

INTEREST OF PROPRANOLOL IN THE TREATMENT OF INFANTIL HEMANGIOMES ABOUT A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY OF 94 CASES

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ABSTRACT Infantile hemangioma (HI) is the most common children 's vascular tumor . It is a benign tumor with essentially clinical diagnosis. Despite its benign character, treatment is required in many situations. This is a retrospective study of 94 outpatients treated with propranolol and followed in the pediatric plastic surgery department (surgery C) at the Rabat Children's Hospital for a period of 4 years from, 2012 to 2017. The average age of children treated was 3 months, with a female predominance (n = 60, 74%).

Tuberous HI was the most common clinical type (n = 68, 70.1%), the single form was predominant (n = 85, 90%), cervico-cephalic localization was the most common (n = 75, 72.1%), labial localization accounted for 40% (n = 30), 6 segmental HIs were reported (6.4%) including 3 PHACES syndromes including Dandy Walker syndrome. The average diameter of HI was 4cm.

Therapeutic indications were for : functional risk (n = 44, 43.5%), ulceration (n = 35, 43.5%), aesthetic risk (n = 20, 20%), and life risk (n = 35, 43.5%), the dosage was 3 mg / kg / day of propranolol . The average duration of treatment was 9 months, the tolerance was good. Only one case of malaise has been reported. Efficacy was very high with 79% success (excellent response (n = 22, 24%), good response (n = 52, 55%)

The follow-up after the end of the treatment did not objectify any recurrence.

KEYWORDS hemangioma, benign tumor, child, evolution, abstention propranolol, benefit - risk, functional and vital prognosis

giomas. Its benefit/risk balance is exciting and has supplanted the general corticosteroids. [2]

Introduction

Infantile hemangioma is a benign vascular tumour, the most common of children's tumours [1], which evolves in three phases: proliferation, stabilization and regression. Because of its spontaneous involution, therapeutic abstention is the rule. Propranolol is systemically effective in severe infantile heman-

Methods and Results

Our study concerned 94 patients treated at the Pediatric Plastic Surgery Hospital in Rabat. The information is collected from a computerized database, as well as photos taken after parental consent for monitoring the evolution. The diagnosis of infantile hemangioma requiring treatment with propranolol is clinical; the complementary examinations are indicated for the segmental hemangiomas likely to be associated with other pathologies. We used propranolol tablet avlocardyl 40 mg. The age of start of treatment is three months; it is continued until the end of the first year of life, this is the theoretical period of proliferation of I HI. For patients older than three months the duration is six months on average. The pre-therapeutic assessment includes a

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fasting blood glucose, an ECG and a cardiologist doctor opinion to eliminate any contraindications for the use of beta-blockers (bronchiolitis, conduction disorders, hypoglycemia predisposition ...) The treatment is started outpatient with an induction dose of 1mg /kg/day, with advice for parents including post-prandial treatment to avoid hypoglycemia and cover the portion of the tablet to avoid the bitter taste that may be discouraging and may affect the adherence to treatment). Monitoring is required to detect hypoglycemia or hypotension. The control is done one week later to evaluate the tolerance and the response to treatment, then increase the dosage to 2 mg/kg/ day. A second test is again performed after one week to reach the dose of 3 mg/kg/ day. Monitoring becomes monthly to evaluate the response to treatment and to adjust the dosage according to weight. For ulcerated hemangiomas, in addition to propranolol, they are treated with fusidic acid ointment as well as an analgesic for pain. Digital photography is systematic during each visit for follow-up and documentation (colour change, volume reduction, healing of ulceration).

In our series, 60 patients are three months old (64%), six are two months old (6%), four patients are respectively 4.6, ten months and two years old (4% each), three children aged five months (3%). Moreover, one child for the following ages: 1 month, seven months, one year, 14 months, 15 months, 17 months, 20 months, three years and five years. The average age is three months. Including 60 girls and 34 boys We have 68 tuberous hemangiomas (70%), 16 mixed (16.5%) and 13 subcutaneous or deep (13.5%). For 85 patients(90%) the HIs are unique, and multiples for nine patients (10%). We have 75 cephalic HI (72.1%), ten at the limb level (9.6%), six at the gluteal region. 4 At the back, three on the flank and two on the sacrum, then one HI in the vulvar, scrotal, anal and thoracic locations. Regarding the therapeutic indications, we have 2 cases (2%) with vital risk: 1 HI systematized S3 of the face with laryngeal involvement, and a columellar hemangioma obstructing the breathing ways. We had 44 cases (43.5%) with functional risk, including 30 labial hemangiomas with the risk of labial incontinence and slurred speech, and 12 orbito-palpebral hemangiomas with the risk of amblyopia and 35 ulcerated hemangiomas that motivated the treatment. (34.5%) Also and finally an aesthetic indication in 20 cases (20%). Duration of treatment is nine months for 66 patients (70%) who was started at three months of life. For all the others it did not exceed six months. The average duration of treatment is nine months. Tolerance is good; no adverse effects have been reported in our series. One discomfort case is reported for a 2-month-old girl after treatment, which imposed temporary suspension of treatment for one month, then her recovery without any incident.

The efficiency is judged about the decrease in the volume of the HI and the change of its colour. , Ulcerative healing for ulcerated hemangiomas, palpebral opening for palpebral HI and suction enhancement and labial continence for labial HI.

In our series The response to treatment was judged:

Excellent in 22 (24%) patients, including 11 ulcerated HIs.

Good in 52 (55%) patients including 24 HI ulcerated

Moderate in 12 cases (13%).

Poor in 6 patients (6%) with the option of surgical intervention at the end of treatment for volume reduction.

Lack of response in 2 patients (2%); a 3-month-old girl with a right tuberous orbito-palpebral HI treated for six months with propranolol combined with corticosteroids without result. A 5-year-old boy with a tuberous HI of the tip of the nose, in these

Fig.1.

patients a surgical reduction is indicated

Discussion

The etiopathogenesis of HI remains misunderstood. Several studies have been conducted to elucidate the mechanism of their development. It is a complex mixture of cells comprising a small proportion of multipotent stem cells (CD133 +), a majority of immature endothelial cells (CD31 +), pericytes (SMA +), dendritic cells (factor XIIIa +), mast cells and mesenchymal cells with adipogenic potential [3]. The endothelial cells of CD 31+ hemangiomas in the proliferative phase are from the same clone [3, 4] During the involution phase; the endothelial cells express markers of apoptosis. In the proliferative phase, it also contains mesenchymal cells with adipogenic potential. Differentiation in adipocytes occurs during the involution phase [5]. The factors that regulate the growth and involution of hemangiomas are still poorly understood; several hypotheses have been advanced concerning the initiator phenomenon [6, 7]:

Somatic mutation, in an endothelial cell precursor, with the colonization of the dermis by angioblasts that are aberrantly differentiated [8].

- Embolization of placental endothelial cells in the fetal circulation and then in the dermis [9].

- Antenatal hypoxia or neonatal stress.

In total, the effectiveness of propranolol is 74% between an excellent and good response, which can make it the first - line treatment. Follow - up of the patients, after the end of the treatment, did not objectify any recurrence; recolouring or re-increasing the HI volume. The size is variable from one patient to another with extremes ranging from 0.5 cm to 18 cm. The average size of hemangiomas is 4 cm, more than 83% of HI are less than or equal to 5 cm.

The majority of HIs are benign and do not require any treatment. Their natural evolution is towards regression, and spontaneous healing Treatment is necessary to avoid and treat the complications related to the transformation of Hi at the local or the

Fig.2.

general level, Propranolol is a non-cardioselective beta-blocker with no intrinsic sympathomimetic activity, which has an interesting balance between benefits and risks. It has gradually supplanted the general corticosteroid therapy in the treatment of complicated HI. Its effectiveness in HI results in sagging and discolouration of the lesion; which is almost constant, particularly fast during the proliferative phase of HI and objective in two months [10]. The treatment results in more or less complete regression of HI. In the most favourable cases, only a few residual telangiectasies persist at the end of treatment. A resurgence is observed if treatment stopped before the end of the growth period of HI, quantified in one year.

Resistance is possible in some cases which do not progress favourably under treatment [11]. In our series the response to treatment was excellent in 24% of patients, good in 55% patients, average in 13% of patients, poor and absent respectively in 6% and 2%.

The sum of the excellent and good results is 79%. No recurrence is reported after the end of treatment, which is very common in corticosteroid therapy. Medio-facial HI responds poorly to treatment; this location is a factor of poor prognosis. The start of treatment must be done in the hospital with monitoring. It is only introduced from the 35th day of life. Our patients are all followed outpatients.

Tolerance for treatment is very good at therapeutic doses. However, it is necessary to monitor:

- Cardiac function: stop treatment if heart rate lower than 60 bpm or blood pressure higher than 60/40 mmHg.

- Blood glucose: stop treatment if blood glucose is below 40 mg/dl.

- Bronchospasm: suspend treatment in case of disposing bronchitis with sibilants or bronchiolitis. The recovery of propranolol is at a distance from this episode, according to the progressive dosage regimen recommended at the initiation of treatment (if the discontinuation was short-lived, it would be sufficient to perform two days at half-dose). Treatment must be definitive in case of recurrence of these respiratory manifestations.

Fig.3.

- The nightmares: with nocturnal awakenings more frequent under treatment.

In our series tolerance is good, only one case of discomfort has been reported with the transient suspension of treatment, its adverse effects are infrequent and benign and do not require the definitive discontinuation of treatment, unlike previously used treatments that had effects unwanted enhancements at the cost of an unsecured improvement. Systemic corticosteroid therapy was the first-line treatment for HI. Its mechanism of action is not well known [6]. The molecules used are prednisone and prednisolone. In case of too fast decay, there is sometimes an evolutionary rebound. Side effects are often transient (cushinoid facies, insomnia, irritability, gastroesophageal reflux, acne, hair growth, growth retardation, osteoporosis), but some are much more serious, such as hypertension, obstructive hypertrophic cardiomyopathy and adrenal insufficiency. The impact of corticosteroids on immature brains is not yet well studied [12]. Interferon alfa-2a and 2b is an anti-angiogenic by down-regulation of bFGF [6], indicated in severe forms of HI, it is effective [13], but its action is slow. Side effects [14] are frequent, associating fever and muscular pain (flu-like syndrome), especially at the beginning of treatment. Vincristine is an antimetabolic used for severe corticosteroid hemangiomas. Its action is faster but requires the installation of a central venous catheterism. Its side effects are neurological and haematological. As a result of its endothelial antiproliferative action, it is indicated in the Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon, a consumption coagulopathy that complicates certain rare vascular tumours of the infant.

Early surgery, in the growth phase, is indicated only for globular infantile hemangiomas especially on the nose, eyelids and lips. The risk of scarring should always be assessed for possible aftereffect in the event of natural resorption. It is also useful for symptomatic laryngeal hemangiomas [15].

Late surgery occupies an essential place in the repair of cutaneous aftereffect (fibro-adipose residues) and structural, after the disappearance of the hemangioma. It is often coupled with the treatment of telangiectasia by lasers. The pulsed dye laser is

Fig.4.

Fig.5.

effective on the superficial component causing discolouration, and helps to heal some ulcerated hemangiomas [16]. In the early phases, it may be indicated in hemangiomas in superficial, red and shallow layers, located in areas exposed to the eyes (face, hand). It is also indicated for ulcerated hemangiomas to promote healing and pain relief, with local care and fatty dressings. In late stages, it can erase telangiectatic sequelae. CO₂ or Erbium lasers are indicated in late phase also on scars with a smoothing effect of tension. The sessions are painful can be done under general anaesthesia or sedation. Level I or II topical corticosteroids for red and shallow superficial haemangiomas would facilitate palatation in the proliferative phase. Topical imiquimod has the same indications as topical corticosteroids and a pulsed dye laser. [17]. Arterial therapeutic embolization is limited to hepatic hemangiomas with heart failure. Radiotherapy was abandoned despite its undeniable effectiveness, but its long-term risks were heavy (thyroid tumours, cutaneous, cerebral ...)

Given the natural evolution of infantile haemangiomas, the rule is therapeutic abstention (80% of children) [17]. However, the expectation of this regression is not conceivable for all haemangiomas, especially those involving functional, vital and aesthetic prognosis. If all the types of treatment that can be applied during the proliferation phase (systemic corticosteroids, intratumoral injection or local application, ulcer care, oral antibiotics, pulsed dye laser and excision surgery) are added, a therapeutic modality is used in 38% of cases. Pharmacological treatments to stop the growth of an alarming hemangioma are used in about 15% of cases. In our series treatment was initiated because of a functional risk in 43.5% of cases, because of ulceration in 34.5% of cases. The aesthetic risk and the vital risk, not exceptional, motivated the treatment respectively in 20% and 2% of cases. It is noted that the aesthetic concern is gaining more and more interest, and becomes an essential reason for treatment, indeed, many parents, poorly assimilate the benign nature of the lesion and its evolutionary profile with spontaneous regression.

Conclusion

The infantile hemangioma (IH) is the most common infant tumour, of undetermined aetiology it appears in the first weeks of life, and also at birth. Its evolution is typical in three phases. The diagnosis is primarily clinical. Although of a benign nature, they may present complications, both local and general. Treatment is necessary for the event of life-threatening, functional and aesthetic prognosis.

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